

CLASSICAL STERN-GERLACH

A 2023 MAGNETIC CLASSICAL VIEW OF THE 1922 STERN-GERLACH EXPERIMENT

Viewing an old Quantum Experiment through a new Classical Lens to Illuminate Quantum Spin

by

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Abstract

We show how atomic beam splitting is a *classical* phenomenon. In particular, we mathematically demonstrate how the magnetic Lorentz force actually forcefully causes the *classical magnetic splitting* of the beam of neutral magnetic silver atoms, in the world-famous 1922 magnetic silver-atom beam-splitting experiment of Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach.

Introduction

In 1922, Otto Stern (1888-1969) and Walther Gerlach (1889-1979) published their brief, four-page paper entitled *Der experimentelle Nachweis der Richtungsquantelung im Magnetfeld*, (English Translation: *Experimental Evidence for Space Quantization in a Magnetic Field*). [1]

For an intriguing century, this important German-language paper, has been widely regarded by thousands of physicists as the *first* experimental evidence for “*Space Quantization*”, or “*Spin Quantization*”, in a magnetic field.

These early *experimental quantum concepts* of 1922, were quickly extended by others during the 1920’s, to additional quantum notions including “*Quantum Superposition*” of multiple different spins, or multiple different spatial locations, or multiple different momenta, or multiple different quantum states.

This present article of 2023 theoretically postulates (and mathematically demonstrates) that simple straightforward magnetic classical physics can *easily* explain the most-important physical results (atomic beam splitting) of the famous Stern-Gerlach 1922 magnetic experiment.

Classical Magnetic Beam-Splitting

In this paper we theoretically demonstrate how magnetic atomic *beam-splitting* is actually a simple, straightforward, easy-to-understand, *classical phenomenon*.

In particular, we show in detail, how the classical *Lorentz Force* of 1895 (and the semi-classical *Bohr atom* of 1913) can be *used together* to physically (and mathematically) account for *all* of the most-important observed (in 1922) *physical behaviors*, of all of the thousands of tiny neutral magnetic silver atoms, as each one of these individual *magnetic-dipole* atoms passes through the strong, *spatially-varying*, inhomogeneous magnet employed by Walther Gerlach and Otto Stern, in their 1922 Stern-Gerlach Experiment.

Classical Magnetic Beam-Broadening

We also explain how the unfortunate naïve “*beam-broadening-only*” presumption of 1922, can now be finally understood by all today in 2023.

We also explain why there is no longer any *real* need (today in 2023) to continue to intellectually cling to any of the faulty old presumptions of the Stern-Gerlach magnetic experiment of 1922.

What is Space Quantization?

We fully realize that this powerful new classical analysis, of the century-old 1922 Stern-Gerlach magnetic experiment, may be upsetting to some; because it boldly *calls into question* the fundamental meaning of “Space Quantization”, “Spin Quantization”, “Quantum Superposition, and “Wavefunction Collapse”.

We earnestly call upon the worldwide physics community to seek to find a way to discover *any* significant flaw in this present paper; or better yet, to *wisely build upon it* to further classically-illuminate the core nature of “Quantum Spin”.

What is Quantum Spin?

One of the purposes of this present paper is to *prompt* a healthy, deep, worldwide scientific conversation, about the fundamental nature of “*Quantum Spin*”.

We hope this article can act to gently *spark*, the kind of wise, thoughtful, worldwide scientific discussion today in 2023, that *could* have occurred much earlier in 1922, just days after Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach published their famous paper.

How does a Magnetic Beam Split into Two Beams?

How can the presence of a large powerful spatially-varying magnet, *sometimes* cause an incoming magnetic beam (of tiny magnets) to become *classically split* into two separate outgoing magnetic beams?

In this paper, we seek to theoretically explain, and mathematically demonstrate, the exact set of *classical magnetic conditions* that are necessary, and sufficient, to classically produce beam splitting, each and every time.

Beam Splitting versus Beam Broadening

We also seek to theoretically explain, and mathematically demonstrate, what kind of experimental adjustments are necessary and sufficient to physically transform a fully *split beam* into a merely *broadened beam*, and also necessary and sufficient to physically transform the merely *broadened beam* back into a fully *split beam*.

Classical Beam Splitting

We also seek to explain how, why, and when the classical Lorentz force (of 1895) is able to *classically beam-split* an incoming solo beam of tiny classical magnets, into two distinct and separate outgoing beams of “*newly quantized*” (newly polarized) outgoing tiny classical magnets.

Lorentz-Force Beam-Splitting Spin-Quantization

We also seek to explain how the magnetic Lorentz force will *always split* an incoming beam of tiny classical magnets, when all the experimental *magnetic conditions* are *just right*, and in the process always quantize (into exactly two beams) the incoming magnetic-dipole spins, forcing these tiny magnetic dipoles to become “Spin Quantized” in each of the two outgoing beams.

Lorentz-Force Spin-Quantization

We also explain why the two-way magnetic Lorentz force is actually the *only force* needed to explain the magnetic spin quantization (of the beam of neutral silver atoms) that is magnetically-forced upon the traveling neutral silver atoms as they pass through the powerful Stern-Gerlach magnet.

Lorentz Quantization

We also explain why the magnetic Lorentz force of 1895, is the *most likely* causal force actively driving *all* types of magnetic spin quantization in this universe.

Apparently, this powerful, classical, magnetic Lorentz force, can forcefully *quantize* the spin (magnetically force the spin into a particular magnetic dipole orientation) of every elementary particle, whenever (and wherever) it is *allowed to act* on the magnetic dipole of the elementary particle, for *long enough*, to actually do so.

Is it conceivably possible, that neither Walther Gerlach, nor Otto Stern, were fully aware of all of the *beam-splitting implications* of all of these powerful (yet simple) classical Lorentz-force concepts in 1922?

Indeed, it does seem to be really unfortunate (for this whole wide world) that all of these *simple magnetic classical ideas*, were apparently not first and foremost, in the bright talented minds of Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach in 1922.

The 1922 Stern-Gerlach Experiment

In their famous experiment of 1922, Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach passed a beam of neutral silver atoms through a narrow slit, and along a sharp *magnetic knife edge*.

The beam of silver atoms (tiny silver *magnets*) was experimentally observed to be “*split*” by the strong *inhomogeneous* magnetic field, of their powerful Stern-Gerlach (SG) magnet, by observing the silver imprint of thousands of these tiny magnetic silver atoms onto a glass measurement plate.

These glass-plate silver depositions of 1922 reveal that the tiny magnetic neutral silver atoms may have been magnetically-repelled, or magnetically-attracted, by the strong north and south poles of the powerful, non-homogeneous magnetic field.

Finally in 2023, an English Translation!

In 1922, Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach published their exciting paper in the German language for German readers.

It is really surprising to us that such a seminal paper in the realm of experimental quantum mechanics was never translated into English until January 26, 2023, when Martin Bauer, from the Department of Physics, at the University of Durham, in the United Kingdom, undertook this important task. [2]

Magnetic Space Quantization

In the introduction to his 2023 translation, Martin Bauer credits the 1922 Stern-Gerlach paper with reporting “*the first evidence for the **quantization of atoms** in a magnetic field. The atoms have quantum states corresponding to a limited number of possible angles between the directions of the angular momenta of the atoms and the magnetic field, also called **space quantization**.*”

Indeed, in their opening paragraph of 1922, Stern and Gerlach report the following: “[W]e allow ourselves to report in the following that the continuation of these investigations has led to establish **space quantization** in a magnetic field as **a fact**.”

Apparently, Gerlach and Stern failed to recognize in 1922 that their observed *magnetic fact* of space quantization, was just a simple (easy to understand) form of Classical Magnetic Space Quantization.

Classical Magnetic Space Quantization

Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach are not the only bright minds who have *failed to recognize* the simple reality of Classical Magnetic Space Quantization.

For example, during this past century, from 1922 to 2023, some intelligent scientists have persisted in claiming that Stern-Gerlach *space quantization* (or Stern-Gerlach spin quantization) is fundamentally *non-classical*.

And some have claimed that “*quantum spin*” is somehow fundamentally different from “*classical spin*”.

And some say that a “*quantum magnet*” is somehow fundamentally distinct from a “*classical magnet*”.

And some claim that “*quantum magnetic dipoles*” behave unlike “*classical magnetic dipoles*”.

No Such Evidence from Stern-Gerlach

However, in this present paper of 2023, we carefully demonstrate, that the Stern-Gerlach magnetic experiment of 1922 *does not* provide *any* experimental *support* for *any* of these supposed fundamental physical distinctions between “classical” and “quantum”, in the area of spin, or in the area of magnetism, or in the area of magnetic-dipole spin.

Where is the Real Evidence?

Some bright minds may yet still believe that the 1922 Stern-Gerlach magnetic experiment somehow provided actual physical *evidence* that “quantum magnets” behave differently from “classical magnets” with respect to magnetic beam splitting.

For example, in 1998, Bretislav Friedrich and Dudley Herschbach published a paper in MIT Press entitled “*Space Quantization: Otto Stern’s Lucky Star*”. [3]

Otto Stern’s Lucky Star

On page 177 the authors wrote:

*Consequently, the **atomic magnets** that are tilted towards the field direction are attracted to the stronger field region, whereas those tilted away are repelled.*

*The trajectories of atoms emerging from the deflecting magnet, as recorded by deposits on the glass plate, thus reveal the **spatial orientation** of the atomic magnets.*

*With such a setup, Stern predicted that space quantization would produce a **splitting** of the **atomic beam** into two distinct components, since in the ground state of the silver atom, the valence electron was expected to have just one unit of orbital angular momentum ($n = k = 1$, so $m = +1$ and -1 components).*

*For **any classical model**, however, the atomic magnets would be distributed over a **continuous angular range**, so passing through the deflecting field would **not split** the beam but **only broaden it** along the field direction.*

A Missing Magnetic Realization

Is it possible that Friedrich and Herschbach (and many others including Stern and Gerlach) may have *not* fully realized how *easily* a powerful, large, torquing, forcing, classical inhomogeneous magnet can *classically split* a beam of tiny *classical magnets*, by *forcing a change* in the magnetic dipole *orientations* of the tiny classical magnets, with the classical Lorentz force, as each tiny *finite-sized* classical magnet experiences the *spatially-varying* magnetic field of the powerful, large, torquing, forcing, classical inhomogeneous magnet?

Classical Lorentz Beam Splitting

How is it possible that this simple *Classical Lorentz Beam Splitting* has been missed by so many for 100 years?

One of the purposes of this present 2023 paper, is to carefully (mathematically) investigate the following question:

Can a single neutral silver magnetic atom, with its finite spatial size, and with its unpaired outer electron, possibly behave *any* differently (with respect to magnetic beam splitting) from any other tiny classical magnet, in the presence of a powerful, *spatially-varying* magnetic field, such as the inhomogeneous magnetic field deployed by Walther Stern and Otto Gerlach in 1922?

On page 177 of reference [3] the words “*that are tilted*” toward, or away from the “*stronger field region*” seem to indicate, that the authors believed, that the magnetic dipole orientations (of the silver atoms) were already *firmly* established *prior* to the time they entered the strong, inhomogeneous magnetic field.

Exactly *how firm* and steadfast are these tiny silver atomic magnetic dipole *orientations* in reality?

Initial Orientation versus Final Orientation

Did Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach (SG) also believe that their powerful Thousand-Gauss SG Magnet merely revealed the *initial* magnetic dipole orientations that existed *before* the silver atoms came anywhere near their powerful, torquing SG magnet?

It is well-known that a much smaller magnet will (sometimes, when able to) quickly *reorient itself* to become mostly attractive to either the north pole, or to the south pole, of a larger magnet.

When the authors (of page 177) say that the atoms deposited on the glass plate “*reveal the spatial orientation of the atomic magnets*”, are they referring to the initial or final spatial orientation of those silver atomic magnets?

Can a *final* orientation be different, than an *initial* orientation?

What is the *physical* difference, on the one hand, between the unobserved, unmeasured, theoretical **Initial** Space Quantization (and the Initial Spin Quantization, and the Initial Magnetic-Dipole Direction Orientation Quantization) of the neutral silver atoms *before* they come anywhere close to the strong magnetic influence of the strong powerful Stern-Gerlach (SG) magnet, and on the other hand, the observed, empirical, measured, physically-recorded **Final** Space Quantization (and the Final Spin Quantization, and the Final Magnetic-Dipole Direction Orientation Quantization) of the neutral silver atoms, *after* they have passed through the strong magnetic influence of the powerful SG magnet?

Classical Magnetic Beam Splitting?

On page 177, Friedrich and Herschbach seem to distinguish (in their 1998 paper of reference [3]) between “*splitting of the atomic beam into two distinct components*” (i.e., space quantization), and their presumed, purported behavior of classical magnets:

“[For] any *classical* model” which “would be distributed over a *continuous* angular range”.

Interacting Magnetic Torques & Forces

Do Friedrich and Herschbach still believe (today in 2023) that a small classical magnet (like a tiny bar magnet, or a tiny compass needle) could not (sometimes) become dynamically compelled (forced) by an interacting combination of *magnetic torques* and *magnetic forces*, to simply reorient itself to become mostly attracted to either the north or the south pole of a large, torquing magnet, but **not** towards the middle region in between these two strong magnetic poles – in other words, **not** “*distributed over a continuous angular range*”?

By magnetically splitting into two separate atomic beams, did not the tiny neutral silver atom magnets behave exactly like we would logically expect most any other set of tiny classical magnets to classically behave while passing through that Thousand-Gauss magnetic Stern-Gerlach magnet of 1922?

An Old Hypothetical Distinction

The beam-splitting distinction between *classical* and *quantum* behavior of the silver atoms appears to be merely hypothetical at best.

Is it not theoretically possible that at its exact physical core, Quantum Mechanics will become just as *understandable* as Classical Mechanics?

If not, then must we also accept Stern-Gerlach's purported underlying assumption of Initial Space Quantization, whereby every neutral silver atom's magnetic dipole moment was initially pointing either exactly up, or exactly down (and in exactly zero of the myriad other possible magnetic dipole directions), prior to passing through the powerful, spatially inhomogeneous SG magnet?

Who really wants to *continue* to believe in such an illogical absurdity?

In order to further illuminate the actual real physical nature of magnetic quantum spin, let's look closely at some of the interacting dynamic magnetic Lorentz forces that *A Large Powerful Horseshoe Magnet* can force upon a set of tiny classical magnets, that are free to change their magnetic-dipole orientations.

A Large Powerful Horseshoe Magnet

What will happen, when we decide to carefully study, how a *great variety* of many different kinds of tiny magnets, will magnetically behave in the magnetic presence of a large, powerful, torquing, inhomogeneous magnet?

Suppose, for example, that one very large, *giant*, very powerful inhomogeneous *horseshoe magnet* is slowly and carefully lowered down towards a smooth, flat, wooden table, upon which thousands of tiny magnets (like tiny bar magnets, or tiny compass needles) are already distributed randomly across the tabletop.

The thousands of original positions, and thousands of original orientations, of the thousands of tiny magnets, relative to the one location (and the one orientation) of the big strong North (and South) magnetic pole, of the large horseshoe magnet, will *largely* determine how the thousands of tiny magnets *initially* begin to behave, as the large horseshoe magnet continues to be slowly lowered down towards the table's surface.

4 Directions & 4 Magnitudes

As the large horseshoe magnet is lowered ever closer to the thousands of tiny magnets, each tiny magnet will begin to feel a magnetic north-torque induced by the strong horseshoe north pole, and a magnetic south-torque induced by the strong horseshoe south pole.

Each of these two competing magnetic *torques* will try to *twist* each tiny magnet, to align itself with one of the powerful horseshoe magnet poles.

Likewise, each tiny magnet will begin to feel two competing magnetic *forces* that will try to *push* and *pull* each tiny magnet towards either the North or South pole of the powerful horseshoe magnet.

Eventually, the tiny magnets will continue to change their magnetic dipole orientations as they begin to fly upwards into the air, as they are strongly attracted to the powerful horseshoe magnetic field that *reorients* (via north pole and south pole magnetic *torques*) and *gathers* (via *inhomogeneous magnetic-gradient net attraction*) all the tiny magnets, as they fly upwards

into the air and firmly attach themselves to *either* the North pole, or the South pole, of the big powerful horseshoe magnet.

As each tiny magnet slightly changes its orientation, the two torques, and the two forces, *dynamically change* their ***four directions*** and their ***four magnitudes***, as these tiny magnets fly upwards into the air towards the one particular horseshoe magnetic pole, that eventually attracts them the most strongly and successfully.

Deterministic Magnetic Behaviors

There is *nothing* mysterious, or merely-probabilistic, about the dynamic interacting magnetic behaviors of one of these tiny magnets.

A tiny magnet (of every tiny size, shape, and strength) behaves exactly as we understand, and expect that it should magnetically behave, as determined by the classical physics of magnetic forces and the classical physics of magnetic torques.

As for one individual neutral silver ***magnetic*** atom, traveling through the big Stern-Gerlach magnet, its final recorded *observed* position (Final Space Quantization) on the silver-collecting glass plate, depends very *sensitively* upon its original spin orientation, and upon its original position, and upon its original velocity, as it begins its early initial movements towards the *inhomogeneous*, spatially-varying magnetic Stern-Gerlach device of 1922.

Hendrik Antoon Lorentz (1853-1928)

Hendrik Antoon Lorentz derived a simple, accurate, mathematical, and correct electromagnetic *force-law equation* in 1895 [4].

This universal electromagnetic force law is appropriately called ***The Lorentz Force***.

It is a foundational law of this physical universe, that governs electrically charged particles, no matter how large or small, in the presence of a magnetic (or electric) field.

This universal Lorentz Force is *always* present, even for the tiny electrically-charged subatomic particles moving about the *interior* of atoms, as this powerful force fully *penetrates* all atomic orbitals, all atomic nuclei, and all the dynamic *inner* structures of all the subatomic particles.

Indeed, we believe that this simple classical Lorentz Force (of 1895) can completely *demystify* the results of the 1922 Stern-Gerlach experiment, and also, in the process, begin to demystify each and every particle of quantum physics.

The $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Lorentz Force

The magnetic portion of this Lorentz Force is sometimes called the “ $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ ” force, which in the English language is usually referred to as the “*vee cross Bee*” force.

In SI Units, the simple, complete, and universal electromagnetic *Lorentz Force* on a particle of charge q and velocity \mathbf{v} is

$$\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{E} + q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$$

with

\mathbf{F} = **Force** on a particle of velocity \mathbf{v} and charge q ,

\mathbf{E} = **Electric Field**,

\mathbf{B} = **Magnetic Field**,

with \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{v} , and \mathbf{B} , all being **vector-valued functions** of space $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ and time t .

The Universal Lorentz Force Law

This Universal Lorentz Force Law may possibly be the *most important* fundamental force, in this whole physical universe of galaxies, stars, planets, people, particles, molecules, atoms, electrons, and quarks.

It may never be possible to *overstate* the *Universal Importance* of this *Mighty Lorentz Force*:

$$\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{E} + q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$$

and, in general,

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t) = q\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) + q\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

with

$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ = the *vector velocity* \mathbf{v} of one single individual *particle* (with charge q) as it *moves* in three-dimensional *space* $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ and *time* t ,

and with

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{F}(x, y, z, t),$$

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{E}(x, y, z, t),$$

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{v}(x, y, z, t),$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{B}(x, y, z, t),$$

because there really do exist *three* distinct spatial physical *components* $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ of the three-dimensional *physical space* that we (us physical people of Earth) all live, all walk, and all breathe in, as a *function* of *time* t .

A *Forcefield* for our *Spacetime*

Therefore, this Universal Lorentz Force $\mathbf{F}(x, y, z, t)$, is in fact a *Forcefield* of *3D Space* $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$, and *1D Time* t , that may be more-explicitly written as

$$\mathbf{F}(x, y, z, t) = q\mathbf{E}(x, y, z, t) + q\mathbf{v}(x, y, z, t) \times \mathbf{B}(x, y, z, t)$$

where we *explicitly show* that these 4 distinct vector fields (\mathbf{F} , \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{v} , and \mathbf{B}) all *depend deeply* (with *exact physical sensitivity*) on their *exact spatial positions* in x space, y space, and in z space, and also in time t .

The “*vee cross Bee*” ($\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$) Force

The very-interesting “*vee cross Bee*” force, $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$, is often written with a little *cross* symbol “ \times ”, to indicate a *vector cross product*.

In this way, the little mathematical *cross* symbol “ \times ” in $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ simply indicates that the velocity vector \mathbf{v} is simply *crossed* into the magnetic field vector \mathbf{B} , via a mathematical outer “*cross*” product operation.

This *outer cross product* operation, is the standard mathematical “*cross product*” way, of simply *multiplying* two spatial vectors *together*, to form a *new vector*, that always *points* in a *new direction*; with this new direction always being *perpendicular* to *both* \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{B} , at *all* times t , and at *every point* in space $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$, according to the proper “*right-hand*” rule, of the standard mathematically-defined *vector cross product* in $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$.

Electromagnetic Lorentz Force

Therefore, a very *simple* clear way of *writing* this easy-to-understand Lorentz force is simply:

$$\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{E} + q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$$

This is a simple *compact way* of writing our ***Universal Lorentz Force Law***; and it actually really physically means a *whole lot* in our real *physical universe* of real physics.

A Real Force $\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{E} + q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ for a Real Universe

This *Real Physical Force* seems to control our *Real Physical Universe*; and our real physical world of *Real Physics* is this real physical universe, where we are all currently living today here on planet Earth inside our own milky-way galaxy.

This universal real *physical force* $\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{E} + q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ of real physical *electric* fields \mathbf{E} , and real physical *magnetic* fields \mathbf{B} , and real *physical particles* of real physical velocities \mathbf{v} , and real physical *charges* q , may be the real *physical source* of all of the real physical *forces* $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}(x, y, z, t)$, that forcefully act on all the real physical particles that have real *physical positions* in x space, and that have real physical positions in y space, and that have real physical positions in z space, and that have real *physical times* t .

The Spatially Varying Magnetic Field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$

For the special magnetic case of 1922, the stationary Stern-Gerlach (SG) magnet did *Not* change its magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{B}(x, y, z)$ in *time* t .

This stationary 1922 SG magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{B}(x, y, z)$ did *not* change in time; but it *did change* in x space, and it *did change* in y space, and it *did change* in z space.

As a matter of fact, Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach specifically designed their 1922 SG magnet to *maximize* the *spatial gradient* of the magnetic field, to produce an *inhomogeneous* magnetic field that was as *strongly* spatially-varying as possible.

By their *intentional design*, their 1922 SG magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$ had a *different* magnetic-field *direction* for each distinct spatial location $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$.

Also, by their *intentional design*, their 1922 SG magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$ also had a *different* magnetic-field *strength* for each distinct spatial location $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$.

This stationary 1922 Stern-Gerlach magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$, did *not* change in time; but it did spatially change *a whole lot*, in magnetic strength and in magnetic direction, as one moved to different locations in space $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ inside the SG magnet.

Now we can ask this very important scientific question:

Is this *spatial variation* in the SG magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$, what *physically caused* the splitting of the beam of silver atoms in Frankfurt, Germany in 1922?

$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$ Spatial Variation Causes Beam Splitting

It is actually fairly easy to see that it is indeed the *spatial variation* (of the Stern-Gerlach magnetic field) that is the actual *physical thing*, that *physically causes* the one single initial beam of physical silver atoms to *split* into two final separate physical *beams* inside the Stern-Gerlach magnet.

What is an easy way to see that this must, in fact, *always* be the case, for *any* magnetic experiment, including any classical magnetic experiment, that is *similar-enough*, to the Stern-Gerlach magnetic experiment of 1922?

How can the super-simple Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force come to our aid here?

For the special case of the Stern-Gerlach magnetic experiment of 1922, the Electric Field \mathbf{E} was effectively *zero*, so we can simply let $\mathbf{E} = 0$ and simply write

$$\mathbf{E} = 0.$$

And therefore, our Lorentz Force simplifies to

$$\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B},$$

with

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t) = q \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}).$$

This shows that $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t) = q \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{Force}$ on the Silver-Atom Unpaired *Outer Electron*, with its Outer-Electron Velocity $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and with its electric charge q , at spatial location $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ and time t ; and with the magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$ being a stationary, *spatially-varying* inhomogeneous magnetic field.

Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force with Newton $\mathbf{F} = m \mathbf{a}$ Force

Let's go ahead and set the *magnetic* Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force of 1895, fully equal to the *inertial* Newton $\mathbf{F} = m \mathbf{a}$ Force of 1687, to get a simple mathematical equation, that mathematically balances the physical *inertial force* with the physical *magnetic force*, to obtain

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t) = q \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}) = m \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t),$$

with

$q = \textit{electric charge}$ of the unpaired outer *electron*,

$m = \textit{mass}$ of the unpaired outer *electron*,

$\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \textit{acceleration}$ of the unpaired outer *electron*,

$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \textit{velocity}$ of the unpaired outer *electron*,

$\mathbf{x}(t) = \textit{location}$ of the unpaired outer *electron*,

with

B (x) = Magnetic Field *pushing, and torquing, and pulling* on the unpaired outer *electron* via its spatially-varying *Magnetic Lorentz* $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$ *Force*,

and

F (x, t) = Magnetic Lorentz Force *pushing, and torquing, and pulling* on the unpaired outer electron, and trying to *accelerate* the electron velocity, and trying to *change* the electron location; and in the process (because the unpaired outer electron is electrically *bound* to the whole neutral *silver atom*) pushing on the *whole silver atom*, torquing on the whole silver atom, pulling on the whole silver atom, and in the process, accelerating the velocity of the whole silver atom, and *changing* the *location* (and *spin-orientation*) of the *whole silver atom*.

The **acceleration** $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ of the unpaired outer electron, is the *time derivative* of the **velocity** $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ of the unpaired outer electron, which is the *time derivative* of the **location** $\mathbf{x}(t)$ of the unpaired outer electron of the whole neutral silver atom.

Integrating over a Full Electronic Orbit

If we so desire, we can choose to simply *integrate* this simple mathematical equation:

$$q \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}) = m \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t),$$

over the exact *electron-path* of the *unpaired outer electron* as it moves through time t and space $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$, and changes its electron spatial location $\mathbf{x} = (x(t), y(t), z(t))$, over all the times (t) , and over all the spatial electron-position locations $x(t)$, $y(t)$, and $z(t)$, of a *full electron orbit* (with its electron location $\mathbf{x}(t)$, electron velocity $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and electron acceleration $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, all *changing dynamically* in time t and space \mathbf{x} , during one single *full electron orbit* around the *outer parts* of the entire neutral silver atom) of the 1913 Bohr Atomic Electronic Orbital Model (that was certainly available to both Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach since 1913), inside the

unique *spatially-varying* magnetic geometry $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$ of the Stern-Gerlach magnet of 1922.

A Much Easier Way

However, there is actually *a much easier way* to mathematically (and physically) *demonstrate* that this simple Lorentz Force

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t) = q \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}) = m \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t),$$

must *always* induce a ***nonzero*** (finite) ***acceleration*** $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, on the *entire* neutral silver *atom*, causing this whole silver atom to *continually change* its *spatial location* $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$, while any part (or any atomic subregion) of this entire neutral silver atom is located *anywhere* near the Stern-Gerlach magnet's powerful *north pole*, or powerful *south pole*.

Spatially-Varying *Inhomogeneous* Magnetic Field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$

In order to successfully and *more easily* do this, we must keep in mind that the *key physical concept* of these ***two poles*** (the north pole and the south pole of the ***inhomogeneous*** Stern-Gerlach magnet) will almost invariably *push* (and *pull* and *torque*) on different ***atomic subregions*** (of the neutral silver atom) *differently*, due to the strong spatial ***inhomogeneity*** of the 1922 Stern-Gerlach (SG) magnet.

For example, when a single individual neutral silver atom is located somewhere inside the Stern-Gerlach magnet, it is logical that there will always exist a "***North Side*** outer-shell *atomic region*" of the outer electronic shell of the silver atom, which is located spatially *closer* to the *SG North Pole* of the Stern-Gerlach magnet, than it is to the *SG South Pole* of the magnet.

Likewise, it is also logical that there will also always exist a “**South Side** outer-shell *atomic region*” of the outer electronic shell of the silver atom that is located closer to the SG South Pole of the Stern-Gerlach magnet, than to the SG North Pole of the magnet.

In this way, the **North Side** is the *northern* side of the silver atom that is closest to the SG *North* Pole, and the **South Side** is the *southern* side of the silver atom that is closest to the SG *South* Pole.

A Silver Atom and its Unpaired Outer Electron

Some atomic scientists believe that an individual silver atom might have an atomic radius of about *144 picometers*.

The tiny *Compton wavelength* (from Arthur Holly Compton of 1892-1962) of an *electron* is only about *2.43 picometers*.

Might this theoretically indicate that a silver atom might be *nearly* a couple of orders of magnitude *larger* than an electron?

However, the larger *DeBroglie wavelength* (from Louis DeBroglie of 1892-1987) of an *electron* can often become much *larger* than just 144 picometers, for slowly moving electrons.

Is it therefore theoretically possible that this could indicate, in a *physical* sense, that a single individual slow electron might *sometimes* be *larger* than a whole silver atom.

Which is Larger?

So, *which* is *larger*, the unpaired *outer* electron, or the *whole* silver atom?

Or are these two real, *physical things* approximately the *same size*?

How can we *know*, scientifically, for sure?

Some scientists might be tempted to claim that the *unpaired outer electron* moves through space in such a way, that it is forced to *continuously* move through space, as the *outer electron* in the *outer regions* of the silver atom.

How does that *neutral*, magnetic ***silver atom*** really ***move and twist***?

How does its *unpaired*, charged, magnetic ***outer electron*** really ***move and twist***?

Which Moves Faster?

Which moves *faster*, a silver atom, or its unpaired outer electron?

What do *you* think?

Can a whole atom move *faster* than one of its very *own* electrons?

How exactly does an unpaired outer electron *move around* its silver atom?

What is the physical *orbital pattern* of this outer electron?

Can this physical orbital pattern *change*, if this outer electron were ever to become spin-paired with another outer electron?

What kind of magnetic field can cause an electronic orbital pattern to *try to change*?

What is the actual *velocity* of the unpaired outer electron, of a neutral silver atom?

Can a *bound electron* really have a *velocity*, even if it is *tightly bound* to an atom?

Electron Velocity

Some scientists still believe that an electron can have a *velocity*, under certain conditions.

Some scientists even believe that an electron can have a *Compton wavelength*, which gives it a *Compton Size*.

Some scientists may also believe that an electron can even have a larger *DeBroglie wavelength*, which gives it a larger *DeBroglie Size*.

What is Real about the Real Electron?

So, what is the *Real Truth* about the *Real Electron*?

Can a real physical electron really have both a *Size* and a *Velocity*?

Can an individual electron really have actual *physical properties* like location, *size*, position, *velocity*, acceleration, *charge*, mass, angular momentum, spin, *internal physical structure*, and a magnetic dipole moment?

Or can an electron consist of merely a mathematical, uncertain, probabilistic entity, with *no physical properties* whatsoever?

Could an electron possibly have *some* real physical characteristics, but not *all* of them?

Or must a real *physical* electron always have all of them?

What is your favorite electron theory?

Silver Atom *Size* and *Velocity*

How about a *Silver Atom*? Can it have both a *Size* and a *Velocity*?

What about the *unpaired outer electron* of a Silver Atom? Can it also have *both* a size and a velocity?

Can the *size* of the outer electron, and the *size* of the whole silver atom, somehow be *related* to each other?

Can the *velocity* of the silver atom, and the *velocity* of its outer electron, ever become *associated* with each other?

How do they both *behave* themselves in the *spatial presence* of a very strong *inhomogeneous* magnetic field?

Can the super-strong, *spatially-varying* magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$ of a Stern-Gerlach magnet ever become powerful enough to even reach *all the way* into the *interior* atomic *regions* of a silver atom, as well as reach deeply into the *outer reaches* of its unpaired *outer* electron, and thus *deeply affect* the *velocity* (with its electric charge) of this *unpaired outer electron*?

The $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force on an Unpaired *Outer* Electron

Can we all finally say *YES*, the *velocity* of the unpaired outer electron *may* become *modified* by this *spatially-varying* magnetic field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$?

Why not?

What about the $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Lorentz Force -- can this force *alter* a velocity \mathbf{v} in some way? Can it even *forcefully-modify* the velocity \mathbf{v} of the unpaired outer electron?

Is this possible in our real *physical* world?

Why not?

Can this mighty Lorentz force *change* the velocity \mathbf{v} of the *unpaired* outer electron in a *gradual, gentle enough* manner, so that this unpaired outer electron always remains *bound* to its silver atom?

$\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force Transfer from Electron to Silver Atom

When this $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force starts putting a *physical force* on the unpaired outer electron, can *some* of this force also become *transferred* to the whole silver atom, because the unpaired outer electron is still *tightly bound* to the entire silver atom?

Is this *force-transfer* logically and *physically* possible?

The obvious answer is *Yes!*

Given how *tightly bound* the electron is to the atom, how can a magnetic $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force on an unpaired outer electron *forcefully translate* into a $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force on a whole silver atom?

How can this magnetic $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force apply a *different force* to the unpaired outer electron at each *different location* (different electronic orbital phase), as it moves about the *outer regions* of the silver atom?

The Outer Orbital Regions of the Unpaired Electron

Is this possible? Do the magnetic forces, on the unpaired outer electron of the silver atom, actually *vary* with *every different location*, and with *every different orbital phase*, of its outer regional electronic orbits?

The real *physical* reason that each electronic orbital region (*orbital phase*) feels a *different magnetic force*, is because the strength and direction of the magnetic field is *physically different* for each distinct orbital phase (electron orbital region) of the unpaired outer electron's orbit around the outermost regions of the silver atom.

Our Universal Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force works for *All* Atomic Models

Our universal Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force works adequately well, for *All* the various *atomic models* of the *past dozen decades*.

Therefore, this *universal* Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force even *works well enough*, so that it really does *Not* matter whether you *choose to believe* that an electron's angular momentum, and its associated magnetic dipole moment, are always mostly associated with an electron's *intrinsic spin*; or you rather *choose to believe* that an electron's angular momentum, and its associated magnetic dipole moment, are sometimes mostly associated with its spatially-extended *atomic orbits*.

Also, this universal Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force is physically *strong-enough*, so that it does *Not* even matter whether you *choose to believe* that electrons and atoms are comprised of *specifically-defined spatial sizes*, or rather *size-less point particles*, or even if you firmly believe they are cosmically *limited* to merely consist of some mathematically-defined *probabilistic-cloud* wavefunctions.

Some may *still believe*, in 2023, that many valid scientific arguments can be rationally made for any, or all, of these wildly *diverse viewpoints*.

Can this Lorentz $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force be Turned Off?

The *only way to turn off* this deeply pervasive Lorentz $q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Force, is to *physically set* some *vital part* of it to *zero*.

For example, charge $q = 0$, velocity $\mathbf{v} = 0$, magnetic field $\mathbf{B} = 0$, or vector-cross-product $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} = 0$, would certainly be physically setting a vital part to *zero*.

However, in the special magnetic case of the 1922 Stern-Gerlach Experiment we have the following:

The Unpaired Outer Electron Charge q is *never zero*,

The Unpaired Outer Electron Velocity \mathbf{v} is *never zero*,

The Stern-Gerlach Magnetic Field \mathbf{B} is *never zero*,

The vector-cross-product of $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ is only occasionally *briefly zero* for just a set of very *small* super-brief moments in *time* when \mathbf{v} is exactly *parallel* (or exactly *antiparallel*) to \mathbf{B} .

In other words, this deeply penetrating $q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force will (*nearly always*) have a huge *forceful* physical effect on the *physical behavior* of the unpaired outer electron, of a silver atom.

There is *no way* to avoid this.

Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach could *not* avoid this in 1922.

We cannot avoid this in 2023.

This $q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force will *always* control the *interior* dynamics (and *exterior* dynamics) of an electron, and of the particular atom to which it belongs.

An Unpaired Outer Electron *has* Physical Properties

An unpaired outer electron has a set of *Real Physical Properties*.

For example, an unpaired outer electron has a *charge* q , a *mass* m , a *velocity* \mathbf{v} , an *acceleration* \mathbf{a} , and a *position* in space \mathbf{x} .

To deny this is to deny the *physical existence* of the *electron* -- to deny *reality* itself.

How exactly does this simple $q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force *modify* the *physical behavior* of a silver atom's unpaired outer electron?

Perhaps it will be helpful, if we make a simple coordinate system to help us to study this simple $q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ force.

A Simple Coordinate System

How shall we construct our *Simple Coordinate System*?

We can put the exact center of our *Simple Coordinate System* at the exact center of our Stern-Gerlach Magnet (SGM); with the *positive z* direction pointing *upwards* toward the **Top** of the SGM *North Pole*, and with the *minus z* direction pointing *downwards* towards the **Bottom** of the SGM *South Pole*, and with the *positive y* direction pointing **Front** in the *forward* direction of the silver-atom *beam flow*, and with the *minus y* direction pointing **Back** towards the *initial source* of the silver atoms, and with the *positive x* direction pointing to our **Right Side**, if we were facing forwards towards the location that the silver atoms are traveling, and with the *minus x* direction pointing to our **Left Side**.

Now let's consider a single, individual, neutral *silver atom* as being a *sphere* of radius $r = 144$ picometers, with its unpaired outer electron traveling at *velocity* $\mathbf{v}(x, y, z, t)$ *rapidly* around the *outer edges* of our *spherical silver atom*.

This unpaired *outer* electron travels at a *very high* velocity $\mathbf{v}(x, y, z, t)$ *speedily* around the *outside* of our *spherical* silver atom.

This unpaired outer electron traverses *many* different *spatial locations* around, and on the *outermost reaches*, of our spherical silver atom.

6 Spatial Locations

We can choose to *label* just *six* of these many different *spatial locations*, in order to clearly *illustrate* some of the powerful *forces* and strong *torques*, that the stationary SG Magnetic Field $\mathbf{B}(x, y, z)$ puts on our rapidly-traveling unpaired outer electron, which is *always moving* speedily *around* its spherical silver atom at its *rapidly-changing* velocity $\mathbf{v}(x, y, z, t)$.

Here are *six* different spatial *locations* that our unpaired *outer electron* rapidly visits repeatedly:

- (1) Silver Atom *Top*
- (2) Silver Atom *Bottom*
- (3) Silver Atom *Front*
- (4) Silver Atom *Back*
- (5) Silver Atom *Right*
- (6) Silver Atom *Left*

Top Forces & Bottom Forces

During one of the many *Top* times, when our unpaired outer electron is at the very *Top* of our spherical silver atom, our unpaired outer electron will experience a *Top* Lorentz Force given by

$$\mathbf{F}(\textit{Top}) = q\mathbf{v}(\textit{Top}) \times \mathbf{B}(\textit{Top}).$$

Likewise, during one of the many *Bottom* moments, when our unpaired outer electron is at the very *Bottom* of our spherical silver atom, our unpaired outer electron will experience a *Bottom* Lorentz Force given by

$$\mathbf{F}(\textit{Bottom}) = q\mathbf{v}(\textit{Bottom}) \times \mathbf{B}(\textit{Bottom}).$$

Front Forces & Back Forces

Also, during one of the many *Front* events, when our unpaired outer electron is at the very *Front* of our spherical silver atom, our unpaired outer electron will experience a *Front* Lorentz Force given by

$$\mathbf{F} (\textit{Front}) = q\mathbf{v} (\textit{Front}) \times \mathbf{B} (\textit{Front}).$$

And similarly, during one of the many *Back* epochs, when our unpaired outer electron is at the very *Back* of our spherical silver atom, our unpaired outer electron will experience a *Back* Lorentz Force given by

$$\mathbf{F} (\textit{Back}) = q\mathbf{v} (\textit{Back}) \times \mathbf{B} (\textit{Back}).$$

Right Forces & Left Forces

And during one of the many *Right* times, when our unpaired outer electron is at the far *Right* of our spherical silver atom center, our unpaired outer electron will experience a *Right* Lorentz Force given by

$$\mathbf{F} (\textit{Right}) = q\mathbf{v} (\textit{Right}) \times \mathbf{B} (\textit{Right}).$$

And likewise, during one of the many *Left* moments, when our unpaired outer electron is at the far *Left* of our spherical silver atom center, our unpaired outer electron will experience a *Left* Lorentz Force given by

$$\mathbf{F} (\textit{Left}) = q\mathbf{v} (\textit{Left}) \times \mathbf{B} (\textit{Left}).$$

The Bohr Atom of 1913

According to the Bohr Atomic Model [5] of 1913, with the Bohr electrons traveling around the atomic nucleus in exactly *circular orbits*, we can deduce that for every *Bottom* moment that *directly follows* a particular *Top* time, we must have our unpaired outer electron traveling at the very *Top* of its orbit in one particular direction, with its electron *Top* velocity $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}$ (*Top*), as this outermost electron moves around the outermost regions of the spherical silver atom, and then continues moving on down to the very *Bottom* of its atomic orbit, where its velocity $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}$ (*Bottom*) must be in exactly the *opposite* direction with $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}$ (*Bottom*) = $-\mathbf{v}$ (*Top*).

This is *physically* logical, because this is *exactly* how a physical *circular orbit* works.

Opposite Electron Velocities

Therefore, we must have

$$\mathbf{v} (\textit{Top}) = -\mathbf{v} (\textit{Bottom})$$

and this would certainly cause the whole silver atom to experience *only* a simple sinusoidal (*eikonal*) precession of its spin direction -- were it *not* for the *spatial variation* in the Stern-Gerlach Magnetic Field.

Back in 1922, did Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach *somehow forget* that their inhomogeneous magnet had a strong *spatial variation*?

Did Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach *somehow forget* that this magnetic *spatial variation* (magnetic inhomogeneity) means that:

B (Top) does Not equal B (Bottom)

This all-important *vital fact* is that the strength (and direction) of the magnetic field \mathbf{B} (*Top*) at the very *Top* of the outer electron orbit is *not the same* (does not equal) as the strength (and direction) of the magnetic field \mathbf{B} (*Bottom*) at the very *Bottom* of the outer electron orbit.

The Consequence of this Magnetic Spatial Variation

This *Magnetic Spatial Variation* (the fact that $\mathbf{B} (Top)$ does not equal $\mathbf{B} (Bottom)$) has some very *huge* mathematical (and physical) *consequences*.

Here are the magnetic Lorentz Force mathematical consequences:

$$\mathbf{F} (Top) = q\mathbf{v} (Top) \times \mathbf{B} (Top),$$

$$\mathbf{F} (Bottom) = q\mathbf{v} (Bottom) \times \mathbf{B} (Bottom),$$

Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F} (Top) + \mathbf{F} (Bottom) &= \\ q\mathbf{v} (Top) \times \mathbf{B} (Top) + q\mathbf{v} (Bottom) \times \mathbf{B} (Bottom) &= \\ q\mathbf{v} (Top) \times \mathbf{B} (Top) - q\mathbf{v} (Top) \times \mathbf{B} (Bottom) &= \\ q\mathbf{v} (Top) \times \{\mathbf{B} (Top) - \mathbf{B} (Bottom)\}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have made the simple substitution

$$\mathbf{v} (Bottom) = -\mathbf{v} (Top).$$

The Total Magnetic Force on the Silver Atom

This means that the *Total Magnetic Force* on a neutral *Silver Atom* (averaged over just one full unpaired-outer-electron orbit) will contain this (Top + Bottom) *forceful contribution*:

$$\mathbf{F} (Top) + \mathbf{F}(Bottom) = q\mathbf{v} (Top) \times \{\mathbf{B} (Top) - \mathbf{B} (Bottom)\}$$

and we can see that the simple *magnetic difference* term:

$$\{\mathbf{B} (Top) - \mathbf{B} (Bottom)\} \text{ does } \textit{Not} \text{ equal zero}$$

because the magnetic field \mathbf{B} at the very *Top* of the spherical silver atom is $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B} (Top)$ which is *very different* from the magnetic field \mathbf{B} at the very *Bottom* of the spherical silver atom which is $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B} (Bottom)$.

Silver Atom is *Forcefully Pushed* to a New Location

This means that this *nonzero* (Top + Bottom) *forceful contribution* will simply *push* the silver atom to a *new location* inside the Stern-Gerlach magnet of 1922.

Long Enough to Fully Split the Beam

This is actually a very *big part* of the *full Lorentz reason* why the beam of silver atoms will *often fully split* into two beams, when the incoming beam stays inside the SG magnet *long enough to fully split*, and when the initial incoming beam is *properly balanced* between the north pole, and the south pole, of the spatially-varying Stern-Gerlach magnet of 1922.

If the neutral silver atoms are *allowed* to stay in the presence of the SG magnet for long enough to have their magnetic dipoles *reoriented enough*, to become predominantly attracted to either the north pole, or to the south pole, then the incoming atomic beam will always *split* into two separate outgoing beams of newly quantized spins.

If the speed of the neutral silver atoms is *too large*, or the strength of the SG magnet *too small*, then the beam will only broaden, but *not split* into two beams.

Beam Splitting is *Not* caused by Space Quantization

Initial Space Quantization is *Not* the reason for the beam splitting.

The *spatially-varying* Magnetic Lorentz Force *is* the *Real Physical Reason* for the magnetic beam splitting.

This is how the SG magnet *worked* in February 1922.

This is also how *all* SG magnets *still work* today in 2023.

All magnetic **beam splitting** is physically *caused* by the spatially-varying fully-classical **Lorentz Force**.

All space quantization (and all magnetic spin quantization) is physically-caused by the classical Lorentz magnetic **beam splitting**, as has been explained in great mathematical detail, here in this present 2023 paper.

Space Quantization is caused by Beam Splitting

Space Quantization is *neither* mysterious nor probabilistic.

Space Quantization is *caused* by classical magnetic Lorentz-force beam splitting inside (or near) a big strong inhomogeneous magnet.

Perhaps as more physicists begin to realize this, then the worldwide intellectual tide may come in brighter, allowing *quantum physics* to shed its mystery.

Hopefully in this way, we can all come to understand *quantum physics* as the simple (understandable) *classical physics* that it has likely always been.

Maybe we can all come to also appreciate the role of *non-eikonal magnetic precession* in SG atomic beam splitting.

Non-Eikonal Magnetic Precession

The **Eikonal Approximation** can be made for waves (and wave motions) with *wavelengths* that are *small* compared to the characteristic **scale lengths** of the spatial variations of the *medium* of *wave propagation* or **wave motion**.

This is certainly the case for the SG magnetic experiment of 1922, because the *Electron Compton Wavelength* of the unpaired outer electron is

physically very *small* compared to the *scale length* of the *spatial variations* of the SG Magnet of Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach.

Some very important (and *very revealing*) physical quantities, like ***total wave action*** (and total system *angular momentum*), are *always* conserved, even for ***Non-Eikonal Waves***. [6]

For our special case, of the Stern-Gerlach Magnetic Experiment of 1922, the SG Magnet has *no temporal variation*, because the SG Magnetic Field does *not* change in time.

Therefore, the Stern-Gerlach *magnetic precession* of the *direction* of the magnetic dipole moment (of the unpaired outer electron) may *sometimes* become somewhat *Eikonal* in time, kind of like a simple *sinusoidal* plane wave.

However, in space, if the *strength* of the Stern-Gerlach Magnetic Field *spatial variation* (spatial gradient) is *strong enough*, in any location inside the Stern-Gerlach Magnet, then the *magnetic precession* of the direction of the magnetic dipole moment (of the unpaired outer electron) may sometimes become ***Non-Eikonal***, with interesting ***spiral motions*** that ***dip***, and ***nod***, and ***pull*** the whole silver atom into different spatial regions of the inhomogeneous Stern-Gerlach magnet.

Non-Eikonal Magnetic Nutation

In addition to the possibility of ***Non-Eikonal Magnetic Precession***, it is also possible for the *direction* of the unpaired outer electron to experience a type of ***Non-Eikonal Magnetic Nutation***, as it *dips*, and as it *nods*, and as it *weaves*, and as it *wanders* through the *spatially-changing* magnetic field provided by the powerful SG Magnet.

The strong magnetic $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Lorentz Force ***causes all*** of these *atomic motions*, as well as the *spiral movements* of the whole spherical neutral *silver atom* into completely-different *spatial regions* of the strong inhomogeneous Stern-Gerlach magnet.

$\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Magnetic Precession & Nutation

It is very easy to see that the $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Lorentz Force is able to *forcefully cause* a tiny magnetic dipole moment (like the unpaired outer electron on a silver atom) to experience a somewhat periodic precession (and a somewhat *periodic nutation*) of the direction (spin orientation) of its tiny magnetic dipole moment.

Because of the detailed mathematical descriptions included in this present article, it should now also become *very easy for all to see*, that the nutation and precession *must also* be accompanied by oscillatory spatial *changes* in the spatial *locations* of the silver atoms.

This *powerful combination* of spatial location change, nutation, and precession, allows the $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ Lorentz Force to gradually *forcefully reorient* a tiny silver-atomic magnetic *dipole* towards one of the two big strong SG Magnetic Poles, and then *forcefully pull* the tiny silver-atomic magnetic dipole (silver atom) towards one of the big strong SG Magnetic Poles.

Magnetic Forced Choosing

In this way, with this combination of non-eikonal nutation, and non-eikonal precession, a large horseshoe magnet can use its powerful magnetic Lorentz force to magnetically “*force*” a set of tiny magnets (like magnetic iron filings or tiny magnetic compass needles) to eventually “*choose*” to either stick to the large horseshoe *north* pole, or to stick to the large horseshoe *south* pole.

A Forced Magnetic Choice between Opposing Poles

In this way, the magnetic Lorentz force, acts upon the moving unpaired outer electron of a neutral silver atom, *forcing* this unpaired electron (and its whole silver atom) to gradually (via non-eikonal nutation and precession) make a *magnetic choice* between the *two* opposing SG magnetic *poles*.

Did both Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach *fully* realize the great importance of the powerful 1895 classical Lorentz force, in magnetically driving this *forced choice* between their SG magnetic north pole and their SG magnetic south pole?

Perhaps not, because their famous 1922 paper did not really discuss the Lorentz force very much at all.

Their famous 1922 paper mostly described their experimental setup and made a rather bold claim about “*space quantization*”.

However, they apparently never even defined what they meant by the words “*space quantization*”.

Why were they trying to discover “*space quantization*”, even though “*space quantization*” was not very well defined?

External Peer Pressure

What was the real reason that Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach continued to work together for so many months, trying to split a beam of silver atoms, after World War I?

What did Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach really *hope* to accomplish with their 1922 magnetic experiment?

Is there any possibility that they were both feeling some *financial pressure*, and some external *peer pressure*, to obtain specific experimental results (measurements and conclusions) desired by others? [7]

Conclusion

What can we finally conclude from this Classical Stern-Gerlach paper?

Our conclusion is that we have logically, rationally, and mathematically demonstrated that magnetic atomic beam splitting can be understood as a *classical* phenomenon.

We have shown that the magnetic Lorentz force of 1895, and the Bohr atom of 1913, are together sufficient to *classically explain* the 1922 Stern-Gerlach beam-splitting of an incoming beam of neutral silver atoms, into two *spin-quantized* outgoing beams of neutral silver atoms.

We have demonstrated how it is the magnetic Lorentz force itself, that *magnetically forces* the spin-quantization to causally take place, inside each silver atom, of the two outgoing beams of neutral silver atoms.

We have explained that this *classical* magnetic atomic *beam splitting* will take place whenever the neutral silver atoms are able to *stay inside* the Stern-Gerlach magnet for *long enough* to have their *spins reoriented* enough, so that each silver atom will gradually become predominantly attracted to either the north pole, or to the south pole, of the Stern-Gerlach magnet.

These tiny magnetic atomic dipole spins really do need *enough time* to *reorient* their directions to one of the two strong Stern-Gerlach magnetic poles.

Therefore, relatively *slow* atom velocities, and relatively *strong*, strongly-inhomogeneous Stern-Gerlach magnets, are actually *needed* for classical Lorentz-force magnetic beam splitting.

In 1922, Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach discovered a *Good Combination* of slow-enough silver-atom speeds, and a strong-enough, strongly-inhomogeneous *Good SG Magnet*, to make this classical Lorentz-force atomic beam splitting to successfully happen inside their Frankfurt, Germany laboratory.

Today in 2023, how can we wisely proceed to construct a set of *Better SG Magnets* to further clarify the physical nature of classical Lorentz-force atomic beam splitting and quantum magnetic spin?

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[7] Note the brief letter that Wolfgang Pauli sent to Walther Gerlach in February 1922 that said “*This should convert even the nonbeliever Stern.*”